

EVALUATION OF VANADIUM IN SELECTED PLANT FOLIAGES

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ABSTRACT

The vanadium content of forty plant foliages were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometry. The foliages were sun dried for eight days, ground, sieved and ashed in muffle furnace. The ashed samples were dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid. Vanadium was determined in the solutions using atomic absorption spectrophotometer. Results depicted the presence of vanadium between ND (*Manihot palmeta*, *Pisidium quajava*) to 9.92mg/kg (*Colocaxia esculenta*).

KEYWORDS: Vanadium, green plant foliages, cholesterol, sugar metabolism

INTRODUCTION

Vanadium is a compound that occurs in nature as a white-to-grey metal and is often found, as crystals pure vanadium has no smell. It usually combine with other elements such as oxygen, sodium, sulfur, or chloride vanadium and vanadium compounds can be found in the earths crust and in rocks, some iron ores and crude petroleum deposits (Nechay, 1984).

Vanadium is mostly combined with others to make special metal mixtures called alloys. Vanadium in the form of vanadium oxide is a compound in special kinds of steel that is used for automobile parts, springs and ball bearings most of the vanadium used in united states is used to make steel, vanadium oxide is a yellow – orange powder, dark gray flakes or yellow crystals (Halberstam *et al*, 1996).

Vanadium is used in metal alloys, important in the production of maleic anhydride and sulfuric acid.

Vanadium also occurs naturally in seafood, meat, dairy foods, cooking oils, fresh fruit and vegetables (Nielsen, 2010).

Foliages are mostly of green colour, more or less dark. They occupy nearly two thirds of cultivable land, foliages are classified according to their importance.

Green plant foliage crops supply most of the vitamins that are needed by higher and lower animal.

Foliage that are cut early are higher in protein, digestible carbohydrates, minerals and carotene than those cut at more mature stages. Late-cut forage are higher in fibre, lignin and cellulose, which are less desirable materials.

Foliage can also be used for making hay for live stock animals, succulent part of the green plant foliage are best use in making hay because this succulent part contains high quality of protein, mineral but less fibre.

Foliage that possesses high protein content must have at least 70 percent in very leafy, and this show that protein content as related to leafless of the plant. As the percentage of leaves decreases and so does the protein content.

Foliages are also higher than the stems in calcium and phosphorous. The most valuable source of vitamin A. A direct relationship between colour, chlorophyll and carotene (vitamin A) content is found in foliage. The deeper the green colour, the higher the vitamin A potency (Ahlgren, 1939).

Foliage like grasses and other leguminous foliages like *Centrocema pubescence*, leafy vegetable e.t.c. can be used as mulching materials either

As to add to the nutrient of the soil or to protect the soil against solar energy especially during the dry season. Foliages can also act as mulching materials for the protection of the soil against erosion, wind, heavy rainfall and predator.

The objective of this study is to determine vanadium content in different plant foliages collected in Akure, Ondo State.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection

The foliages of plants used for this determination were collected early in the morning within the hours of 7-10 am in June 25th, 2006.

The collection was carried out within the school premises of Federal College of Agriculture, Ondo State, Akure. The samples were identified and well labeled. Most of the samples (Table 1) were collected at Horticulture and Tree Crop Unit of Federal College of Agriculture, Akure, Ondo State.

Samples preparation

The leaves were sun dried for eight days after drying the leaves were ground into powdery forms, using mortar and pestle, sieved and then stored in different dried containers and labeled.

Each samples (0.5g) were measured into a clean crucible (A1). The crucibles were then placed into the muffle furnace set at about 555^oC and ashed for about 3 h.

Determination of minerals

The ashed samples were dissolved in 20cm³ of dilute HCl, filtered, made up to 50cm³ with dilute HCl and transferred into specimen bottles. Vanadium values of the samples were determined in triplicate by means of an atomic absorption spectrophotometer following manufacturer specification and procedures.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the value of Va in the different samples. It was observed that foliages have different values of vanadium ranging from 1.24 – 9.92 mgkg⁻¹. The result of study undertaken by Myron *et al.*, (retrieved in 2010) showed that beverages, fats and oils, fresh fruits and vegetables contained the least vanadium ranging from < 1 to 5 mgkg⁻¹. Whole grains, seafood, meats and dairy products were generally within the range of 5 to 30 mgkg⁻¹. Prepared foods ranged from 11 to 93 mgkg⁻¹. It could be deduced that some of our results compared with these. The variations observed were probably usual since Va contents of any crop are likely to vary due to various factors such as trace metal content of the soil, metal constituents of water used, geographical location and fertilizer and fungicides applied. Contamination of soils and crops by the metals through atmospheric deposition has also been established. (Mattigod, 1983).

Vanadium is a metallic element that only exists in combination with other minerals and never in its pure state. One of them, Vanadyl sulfate, has been used to increase insulin sensitivity in supplements and has therefore been targeted at diabetes sufferers and the body-building market.

Vanadium is a little known mineral that may actually be required for maintaining health, although no clear scientific proof of this exists at present. Bones and teeth may use vanadium as a building material. Vanadium also plays a role in blood sugar balance and cardiovascular function, it helps reduce the production of cholesterol and helps the body with sugar metabolism (Dummies.com, 2010).

No RDA for vanadium exists. The average person may consume 2-15ng daily, and therapeutic levels are about 15-25mg daily. Even higher amounts are sometimes used for diabetics (Nielsen, 2010)*F. H. n3*.

Vanadium appears to be nontoxic, and the consequences of deficiency are unknown. Excesses of vanadium have been associated with manic depression (Dummies.com,2010).

In 2003, The UK Food Standard Agency's Expert Group on vitamins and minerals determined over exposure to vanadium could cause, cramps, loosened stools, green tongue as well as fatigue and lethargy. In vivo studies indicate vanadium could adversely affect male and female reproduction as well as infant development (Starling, 2008).

The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) has rejected vanadium as an ingredient that can safely be used in foods and food supplements because of overexposure fears to the general population.

EFSA's Panel on additives, flavourings, processing aids and materials in contact with food (AFC) delivered negative verdicts on six vanadium-containing compounds. Vanadium forms are typically used as a dye and colour-fixer in foods and supplements (Starling, 2008)

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Table 1: Samples used for the analysis

English Name		Botanical Names	
1.	Teak	<i>Tectona</i>	<i>grandis</i>
2.	Lemon	<i>Citrus</i>	<i>limon</i>
3.	Mango	<i>Mangifera</i>	<i>indica</i>
4.	Copper leaf	<i>Acalypha</i>	<i>ciliate</i>
5.	False vervain	<i>Stachytarpheta</i>	<i>cayennensis</i>
6.	Cotton	<i>gossypium</i>	<i>hirsutum</i>
7.	Plum	<i>Spondias</i>	<i>mombin</i>
8.	Plantain	<i>Musa</i>	<i>paradisiaca</i>
9.	Water leaf	<i>Talinum</i>	<i>triangulare</i>
10.	Pawpaw	<i>Carica</i>	<i>papaya</i>
11.	Ocimum	<i>Ocimum</i>	<i>gratissimum</i>
12.	Fluted pumpkin	<i>Telfaira</i>	<i>accidentalis</i>
13.	Drum skick	<i>Moringa</i>	<i>oligofera</i>
14.	Grap fruit	<i>Citrus</i>	<i>paradise</i>
15.	White yam	<i>Dioscorea</i>	<i>rotundata</i>
16.	Sweet cassava	<i>Manihot</i>	<i>palmate</i>
17.	Bitter leaf	<i>Vernonia</i>	<i>amygdalina</i>
18.	Guava	<i>Psidium</i>	<i>guajava</i>
19.	Cocoyam	<i>Colocaxia</i>	<i>esculenta</i>
20.	Sandpaper leaf	<i>Ficus</i>	<i>exasperate</i>
21.	Dongoyaro	<i>Azadirachta</i>	<i>indica</i>
22.	Pepper	<i>Capsicum</i>	<i>annum</i>
23.	Coconut	<i>Coco</i>	<i>nucifera</i>
24.	Aspilia	<i>Aspilia</i>	<i>Africana</i>
25.	Dilpalm	<i>Elaeis</i>	<i>guineensis</i>
26.	Lime	<i>Citrus</i>	<i>antifolia</i>
27.	Cowpea	<i>Vigna</i>	<i>unguiculata</i>
28.	Sugar cane	<i>Saccharum</i>	<i>officinarum</i>
29.	Flamboyant tree	<i>Delonix</i>	<i>regia</i>
30.	Orange	<i>Citrus</i>	<i>sinensis</i>
31.	Draw leaf	<i>Cochorus</i>	<i>olitorus</i>
32.	Maize	<i>Zea</i>	<i>mays</i>
33.	Kolanut	<i>Cola</i>	<i>nitida</i>
34.	Masquerate tree	<i>Plyalthia</i>	<i>pendula</i>
35.	Wild oil nut	<i>Jatropha</i>	<i>curcas</i>
36.	Okro	<i>Hibiscus</i>	<i>esculentum</i>
37.	Gliricidia	<i>Gliricidia</i>	<i>sepium</i>
38.	Rubber	<i>Hevea</i>	<i>brasiliensis</i>
39.	Cocoa	<i>Theobroma</i>	<i>cacao</i>
40.	Chromolaenae	<i>Chromolacnea</i>	<i>odorata</i>

Table 2: The values of the mineral (mgkg⁻¹) determined

Samples			Values
1.	<i>Tectona</i>	<i>grandis</i>	1.24
2.	<i>Citrus</i>	<i>limon</i>	2.48
3.	<i>Mangifera</i>	<i>indica</i>	1.24
4.	<i>Acalypha</i>	<i>ciliate</i>	1.24
5.	<i>Stachytarpheta</i>	<i>cayennensis</i>	2.48
6.	<i>Gossypium</i>	<i>hirsutum</i>	1.24
7.	<i>Spondias</i>	<i>mombin</i>	1.24
8.	<i>Musa</i>	<i>paradisiaca</i>	3.72
9.	<i>Talinum</i>	<i>triangulare</i>	2.48
10.	<i>Carica</i>	<i>papaya</i>	3.72
11.	<i>Ocimum</i>	<i>gratissimum</i>	4.96
12.	<i>Telfaira</i>	<i>occidentalis</i>	2.48
13.	<i>Moringa</i>	<i>oligofera</i>	3.72
14.	<i>Citrus</i>	<i>rotundata</i>	1.24
15.	<i>Dioscorea</i>	<i>rotundata</i>	1.24
16.	<i>Manihot</i>	<i>palmate</i>	ND
17.	<i>Vernonia</i>	<i>amygdalina</i>	1.24
18.	<i>Psidium</i>	<i>guajava</i>	ND
19.	<i>Colocaxia</i>	<i>esculenta</i>	9.92
20.	<i>Ficus</i>	<i>exasperate</i>	4.96
21.	<i>Azadirachta</i>	<i>indica</i>	3.72
22.	<i>Capsicum</i>	<i>annum</i>	3.72
23.	<i>Coco</i>	<i>nucifera</i>	6.20
24.	<i>Aspilia</i>	<i>Africana</i>	4.96
25.	<i>Elaeis</i>	<i>guineensis</i>	2.48
26.	<i>Citrus</i>	<i>antifolia</i>	3.72
27.	<i>Vigna</i>	<i>unguiculata</i>	4.96
28.	<i>Saccharum</i>	<i>officinarum</i>	2.48
29.	<i>Delonix</i>	<i>ragia</i>	2.48
30.	<i>Citrus</i>	<i>sinensis</i>	3.72
31.	<i>Cochorus</i>	<i>olitorus</i>	4.96
32.	<i>Zea</i>	<i>mays</i>	3.72
33.	<i>Cola</i>	<i>nitida</i>	1.24
34.	<i>Plyalthia</i>	<i>pendula</i>	2.48
35.	<i>Jatropha</i>	<i>curcas</i>	4.96
36.	<i>Hibiscus</i>	<i>esculentum</i>	2.48
37.	<i>Gliricidia</i>	<i>sepium</i>	4.96
38.	<i>Hevea</i>	<i>brasiliensis</i>	4.96
39.	<i>Theobroma</i>	<i>cacao</i>	7.44
40.	<i>Chromolacne</i>	<i>odorata</i>	3.72

ND – Not detected.

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